

Notes

The absorption spectra of cobaltglycinate complex and field stabilisation

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BOTH anions and cations absorb in the U.V. region of the spectrum. These absorption bands were first interpreted as charge transfer bands by Frank and Scheibe¹. These authors believed that absorption of light by a hydrated negative ion was accompanied by the formation of a free radical and hydrated electron. The nature of the charge-transfer process responsible for the cation bands is not as obvious as in the case of anions. Rabinowitch² suggests that in the case of easily oxidised cations the charge transfer absorption of longest wavelength is from the ion to the solvent while in easily reduced cations it is in the opposite direction. Work by Dainton³ suggests that the minimum energy of the charge transfer process for ions of the type M^{2+} may correspond quite closely to the energy of the process

In these ions it seems certain that the charge transfer process is from bivalent ion to solvent.

Pauling⁴ believed that the ionic complexes are in fact covalent. Graddon⁵ has suggested, working on complex oxalates, that a low intensity absorption band at about 250 nm, distinguishable only in cases where it is not swamped by the main charge transfer band occurring usually at shorter wavelengths, can be attributed to transitions of the π -electrons of the carbonyl in situations in which the carboxyl group is covalently bound, since the two oxygens will be in this case unequivalent. He found that in the case of complexes with metal ions especially trivalent ion that evidence pointed to these complexes being of the outer orbital, covalent type. Evidence in the case of oxalate complexes of divalent iron, cobalt, nickel and tin however was inconclusive.

Experimental

A solution of carbonate free NaOH was prepared by pipetting saturated NaOH solution into the vessel of an automatic burette containing conductivity water through which nitrogen had been passed for 1 hr. Bubbling of the nitrogen was continued while saturated NaOH was being added and for some time after addition. Both inlets to the automatic burette were then closed with tubes containing

sodalime. The carbonate free NaOH was standardised by titration against potassium hydrogen phthalate.

Approximately molar stock solution of cobalt chloride was prepared using the analar reagent, cobalt chloride hexahydrate being dissolved in conductivity water. The solution was standardised using an ion exchange resin, Amberlite IR 120, which had been converted to hydrogen form by washing with HCl and finally with distilled water until the washings were neutral. The stock solution was diluted ten times and known quantities of the resulting solutions were slowly washed through the column containing the resin, washing with distilled water being continued until neutrality of the eluant was again achieved. From these titrations the exact molarity of the stock solution could be obtained.

A standard glycine solution was prepared by weight from the analar reagent and appropriate quantities of this solution and standard NaOH were added together to produce sodium glycinate solution.

Cobalt hydroxide precipitated out above $pH=9$ and that at pH values greater than 7 crystals of an insoluble complex formed when the solution was allowed to stand for a short time. Standard HCl acid was added to the solutions to a level at which no precipitation occurred.

Apparatus

Optical density measurements were made on a Hilger Uvispec Spectrophotometer using a hydrogen lamp to obtain wavelengths from 180 nm to 360 nm and a tungsten filament lamp as a source of wavelengths above 360 nm.

The stoppered silica glass cells of 1 cm thickness were efficiently cleaned by standing in chromic acid for 10 min, and were stored in distilled water.

A Cambridge pH meter with a cell consisting of a glass and calomel electrode was used to determine the pH values of solutions.

All glass apparatus was "Grade A" quality and was cleaned for at least half an hour with chromic acid. It was stored in distilled water when not in use. Glass apparatus was dried with analar acetone.

Results

TABLE 1. WAVELENGTHS OF MAXIMUM ABSORPTION FOR METAL (1) WATER-SYSTEM

Reaction :			λ_{max}
$Co^{2+}(aq)$	$-Co^{3+}(aq)$	$+e^{-}(aq)$	196 nm
Graph (1)	cobaltglycinate (absorbing species)		λ_{max} 205 μm

TABLE 2. CONCENTRATION OF SUBSTITUENTS IN SOLUTIONS GIVING RISE TO GRAPH 2

Graph (2)	Solution 0.1016 CoCl ₂
From	510 nm (λ_{max}) 0.497 (O.D.)

Discussion

The graph in Fig. 1 shows how the optical density varies with the wavelength of the light passed through 0.01M sol of cobalt glycinate.

These results show that the predominant electron transfer process is from the anion to the cation, since Ni will more readily be an electron than Co, which conversely shows a greater tendency towards electron release.

The graph on Fig. 2 shows the variation of optical density with wavelength when Co(II) is the cation. Only a very small shift in wavelength occurred between Co and its complexes and in this case the complex absorbed at slightly longer wavelength. Further investigation using cobalt had to be abandoned since even the above mentioned slight shift

in spectrum could not be detected when concentrations were reduced, due mainly to the suppression of complex formation, a result of the necessity of working below pH 7.

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3, 5, 5-Trimethyl-1-aryl-2-pyrazolines: Biologically Active Agents

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CHETKOV *et al* have reported that 2-pyrazolines are valuable as corrosion inhibitors¹, and some have been tested for their fungicidal action². But a perusal of available literature does not seem to indicate a further study of the same.

3,5,5-Trimethyl-1-aryl-2-pyrazolines may be easily obtained by the reaction between mesityl oxide and arylhydrazines³. The 1-phenylpyrazoline (I) has been chlorosulphonated⁴ to yield the corresponding 1-(*p*-chlorosulphonylphenyl)-pyrazoline (II) which was

